

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

DIGITALIZATION OF EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8037238>*

Abstract

The article considers the peculiarities of informatization of modern general education, in which a new direction - education for sustainable development - is becoming more and more important, a system-forming vector in the world educational process. It is proved that accessibility of education, which acquires the properties of trans-disciplinarity, aspectuality, huge spatial and temporal scales, becomes more and more abstract and abstract, becomes impossible without information and communication technologies. Examples of artificial intelligence, distributed registry technologies, and zero-disclosure evidence are examined.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, blockchain, zero-disclosure proof, education for sustainability.

Monitoring of education, which is held annually under the auspices of UNESCO, monitors the dynamics of the implementation of education for sustainable development in different countries around the world. One of the key conclusions of such monitoring is that no country has yet ensured the implementation of education for sustainable development at the national level. The options of interaction between the content of school subjects and the content of education for sustainable development have been considered [15;16;17]. It is concluded that only the option of "embedding" gives an opportunity to move away from the option "two objectives of the educational subject". [11].

Let us consider some "hot areas" of education for sustainable development for which information and communication technologies are critical.

Integrated nature of culture for sustainable development. This nature of culture involves the interaction of different educational subjects in the paradigm of culture, rethinking the content of education, the structure of educational subjects, technologies, methods and techniques of education [3;5]. The large amount of data that arises in solving this task requires the use of information technologies - artificial intelligence and blockchain. These technologies allow to single out explicit and implicit values of culture of sustainable development in the content of educational subjects, to systematize them, to reveal deficiencies, "gaps" in the integral image of culture in order to fill them [1;2].

Formation of bases of new culture - culture of stable way of life which bears vital values of global citizenship and sustainable development [10]. They are based on the understanding of the relationship between the global and local, past and future, the problems of the natural environment with social and economic issues [18]. It is an understanding and acceptance of a

qualitatively new value of the 21st century - the ecological imperative. Acceptance of the ecological imperative is the answer to the worldview question about the place of man on the planet. Is man the master of the Earth, the crown of nature, who by his status as a rational being can manage it? Or is man a biosocial being, for whom the preservation of the natural environment (his ecological niche) is a condition of survival on Earth, for which he must learn to manage himself. Naturally, the formation of the value of the ecological imperative requires the visualization of this phenomenon with the help of associations, metaphors, symbols, signs. Here artificial intelligence is indispensable [6].

Integrating the content for sustainable development are the cross-cutting content areas of the Sustainable Development Goals [4;12;19]. These are

planet - environmental sustainability, preservation of the natural environment, natural diversity, restoration of damage, precaution; interdependence of ecological, social and economic systems;

prosperity - increasing prosperity and green economy, improving the quality of life of people (improving health, increasing life expectancy, getting the necessary education, guaranteeing freedoms, rights, etc.), meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs

people - social sustainability, eradication of poverty and indigence, mitigation of wealth inequalities, democracy and civil society; fostering global citizenship;

Peace - the elimination of all forms of violence against man and nature; the absence of war, terror and ecocide, justice, cultural diversity;

residence - sustainable development of cities, settlements;

cooperation, partnership, including international cooperation and global partnership [13].

How to present these global concepts to a child? It is important to note that the ways teachers like to organize students' activities - educational projects, educational research - are inapplicable to the study of such a mega-system as the planet, to which the experiment is not applicable [7]. This means that here we cannot do without the technology of proof with zero-disclosure in cryptography [9]. This is a method that allows one to verify the validity of a statement without having any other additional information. Zero-disclosure proof is used in several blockchains. Blockchain, a distributed data technology, allows fragments of content from different subjects to be "embedded" in each area of the Sustainable Development Goals, forming the basis for interdisciplinarity in their study [8].

In countries "smart" schools are appearing in which on the basis of artificial intelligence, neural networks the functioning of interdisciplinary courses which allow to "see" the global processes and their interconnections [1].

Artificial intelligence has a great opportunity to improve the effectiveness of education for sustainable development, to personalize it, to reduce the burden on teachers. Moreover, artificial intelligence allows to build individual learning trajectories. Artificial Intelligence can determine which sections of learning materials are less understandable to students and tailor instruction to each student. It helps teachers evaluate students' work (more objectively) and helps textbook authors improve texts and make them more understandable and accessible.

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DIAGNOSTICS OF THE COORDINATION SKILLS OF PRIMARY SCHOOL-AGE STUDENTS

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ДИАГНОСТИКА НА КООРДИНАЦИОННИТЕ СПОСОБНОСТИ НА УЧЕНИЦИ ОТ НАЧАЛНА УЧИЛИЩНА ВЪЗРАСТ

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Abstract

Motor coordination is an important indicator of a person's level of physical performance. The development of coordination abilities is important for the effective mastery of an arsenal of new motor skills. Indicators of motor coordination are the accuracy and time of execution of motor actions of different coordination complexity, which are directly related to sensory perceptions, the vegetative system and nervous processes.

The article presents a study of the coordination abilities of primary school-aged students, defined as an important sensitive period in the studied area. The scientific research was carried out using the method of testing by means of a test battery of 120 students from the initial stage of the basic educational degree from the city of Stara Zagora. The obtained results show an unsatisfactory level of motor coordination, which is primarily much better developed in boys than in girls. A progressive increase in achievements in terms of age was observed in all the examined persons.

Анотация

Двигателната координация е важен показател за нивото на физическа дееспособност на човека. Развиването на координационните способности е от значение за ефективното овладяване на арсенал от нови двигателни умения. Показатели за двигателна координация са точността и времето за изпълнение на двигателни действия с различна координационна сложност, които са пряко свързани със сетивните възприятия, вегетативната система и нервните процеси.

Статията представя изследване на координационните способности на ученици от начална училищна възраст, определян като важен сензитивен период в проучваната област. Научното изследване е осъществено чрез метода тестиране посредством тестова батерия на 120 ученици от началния етап на основната образователна степен от град Стара Загора. Получените резултати показват незадоволително ниво на двигателна координация, която приоритетно е много по-добре развита при момчетата, отколкото при момичетата. При всички изследвани лица се наблюдава прогресивно нарастване на постиженията във възрастов аспект.

Keywords: motor coordination, students, motor tests

Ключови думи: двигателна координация, ученици, двигателни тестове

Важно място в живота на човека заема движението, което се проявява чрез различните компоненти на физическата култура. Основно средство на

физическото възпитание и всички дейности, свързани с него, са физическите упражнения, които оказват здравословно въздействие върху човешкия